

Modeling the Growth of Research Literature on Pollination: A Scientometric study based on CABI database

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Abstract

Present study demonstrates the growth of research publications on Pollination published by the Indian scientists which indexed in CABI database for the period 1998 to 2022 (25 years). The study found that total 1325 research publications, there is no consistent growth of publications for entire study period, varies between 3.87% (38) to 4.68% (62) publications, except for the year 2021 with 5.36% (71) and for the year 2014 with 6.49% (86) highest publications. Relative Growth Rate (RGR) decreased from 0.70 in the year 1998 to 0.05 in the year 2022. The Doubling Time (Dt.) of publications increased over period from 0.98 in the year 1998 to 14.46 in the year 2022. The distribution for literature is negatively skewed for all the block periods except 2013-2017. Growth of Pollination literature does not fit for Linear, Exponential and Power trend lines.

Keyword: Scientometric, pollination, plant diseases, bibliometric, growth model.

Introduction

Pollination is the transfer of a pollen grain (male gametophyte) to a flower's stigma (receptive surface of the female reproductive organ), where it may germinate, grow through the style, and fertilize an ovule to produce a seed (Inouye, 2013), Pollination is important for a strong, healthy ecosystem. One in three bites of food you eat depends on pollinators. Successful pollination requires year-round efforts. Plants evolved with differing flowering times that decrease competition among pollinators. Continuous blooms throughout the growing season provide pollinators with a constant food supply (Smithsonian Gardens, n.d.). Pollination improves the yield of most crop species and contributes to one-third of global

crop production, but comprehensive benefits including crop quality are still unknown. Hence, pollination is underestimated by international policies, which is particularly alarming in times of agricultural intensification and diminishing pollination services (Klatt et.al., 2014). Total area of bee dependant crops in India is around 50 million hectare. One hundred and fifty million colonies are needed to meet this, at the rate of 3 colonies per hectare. In India at present, there are only 1.2 million colonies exist. Hence there is a wide scope for expansion of bee keeping for pollination in India (TNAU, n.d.).

Bibliometric and Scientometrics has been broadly used as a quantitative analysis method in many scientific research fields (Rao, 1998). The measurement of bibliographic information offers the promise of providing a theory that will resolve many practical problems (Keshava, Hiremath, Lamani, & Ganjihal, 2009; Keshava, CAN, Ganjihal, & Lokesh, 2010). Using bibliometrics and scientometrics analysis, we can further understand the status and trends of research literature on Pollination, literature growth rates and related statistical distributions can be used to evaluate. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the research publication trends in Pollination research during 1998 to 2022 published by Indian Scientists.

Review of Literature

Karki et al. (2000) investigated the growth trends for India and world organic chemistry, follow the same patterns and the output in the three sub-fields is not going to saturate in the near future. Gupta et al. (2002) observed that the power model ($\alpha > 0, \gamma > 1$) followed by logistic models are best describing the cumulative growth of publications in all sub-disciplines. Sangam, Liming & Ganjihal (2010) studied the growth and dynamics of Indian and Chinese publications in the field of liquid crystals research by applying growth models as suggested by Egghe and Ravichandra Rao (1992), concluded that these power and growth models are likely to be fully applicable in the growth of Indian, and linear, power, and growth models applicable in the growth of Chinese liquid crystals literature. Ganjihal & Keshava (2008) conducted study on Scientometric dimensions of Astronomy and Astrophysics research in India. Ganjihal & Keshava (2015) analysed Radio Astronomy Research in India. Ganjihal & Keshava (2015) analysed the growth pattern of Indian Radio Astronomy literature and also on Chinese radio astronomy literature. Ganjihal et. al. (2023) studied the applicability Bradford's law to the bacterial blight research literature. Ganjihal, Keshava & Sangam (2017) analysed application of Bradford's law in the field of Radio Astronomy Research in India based on Web of Science. Hadagali & Anandhalli (2015) study demonstrates the growth of neurology literature for the period 1961-2010 and interprets that the observed data fit an exponential growth model. Nayak & Bankapur (2018) study demonstrates the modeling the growth of Indian agricultural literature. Ganjihal, Ganjihal & Kwati (2023) demonstrate the growth of bacterial blight, the study observed that, the data fits well for Polynomial growth trend for bacterial blight publications.

The result shows that there are lot of the studies very conducted on growth models on various subject field applying different growth models, but there is no significant study was conducted on growth trend analysis on research literature on Pollination so far.

Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are:

- To identify the growth of Research literature on Pollination by Indian scientists;
- To analyze the fit of Research literature on Pollination publications in terms of different models.

Data and methodology

For the present study, the data was collected from CABI database (includes CAB ABSTRACTS, Horticultural Science, Crop Protection Compendium and Horticulture Compendium) records pertaining to the research publications on Pollination published from India for the period of 25 years from 1998 to 2022, in the month of March 2023. CAB Direct is the most thorough and extensive source of reference in the applied life sciences, incorporating the leading bibliographic databases CAB Abstracts and Global Health (CABI, 2023). Total 1,325 publications were retrieved in plain text format. Further the data was analysed with bibliometric methods quantitatively using MS excel and SPSS software and applied different growth patterns to check whether the Research literature on Pollination is fit for linear, exponential, or power models.

Data analysis and Discussion

Year wise distribution of research literature

Table 1 shows that, the year wise growth of publications, total 1,325 publications were found research literature on Pollination during the year 1998 to 2022. It is observed that there is no consistent growth of publications for entire study period, varies between 3.87% (38) to 4.68% (62) publications, except for the year 2021 with 5.36% (71) and for the year 2014 with 6.49% (86) highest publications.

Table 1 Year wise distribution of Research literature on Pollination

Year	Publications	%	Cumulative Publications	W1	W2	RGR	Mean	Dt	Mean
1998	45	3.40	45		3.81		0.41		2.15
1999	46	3.47	91	3.81	4.51	0.70		0.98	
2000	51	3.85	142	4.51	4.96	0.44		1.56	
2001	49	3.70	191	4.96	5.25	0.30		2.34	
2002	39	2.94	230	5.25	5.44	0.19		3.73	
2003	38	2.87	268	5.44	5.59	0.15	0.14	4.53	5.15
2004	52	3.92	320	5.59	5.77	0.18		3.91	
2005	52	3.92	372	5.77	5.92	0.15		4.60	
2006	45	3.40	417	5.92	6.03	0.11		6.07	
2007	46	3.47	463	6.03	6.14	0.10		6.62	
2008	38	2.87	501	6.14	6.22	0.08	0.09	8.79	7.85
2009	44	3.32	545	6.22	6.30	0.08		8.23	
2010	60	4.53	605	6.30	6.41	0.10		6.64	
2011	60	4.53	665	6.41	6.50	0.09		7.33	
2012	58	4.38	723	6.50	6.58	0.08		8.29	
2013	44	3.32	767	6.58	6.64	0.06		11.73	

2014	86	6.49	853	6.64	6.75	0.11	0.07	6.52	10.02
2015	62	4.68	915	6.75	6.82	0.07		9.88	
2016	61	4.60	976	6.82	6.88	0.06		10.74	
2017	62	4.68	1038	6.88	6.95	0.06		11.25	
2018	61	4.60	1099	6.95	7.00	0.06	0.05	12.14	14.63
2019	51	3.85	1150	7.00	7.05	0.05		15.28	
2020	42	3.17	1192	7.05	7.08	0.04		19.32	
2021	71	5.36	1263	7.08	7.14	0.06		11.98	
2022	62	4.68	1325	7.14	7.19	0.05		14.46	
	1325								

The Relative Growth Rate (RGR) increases in the number of publications per unit of time. This definition was derived from the description of relative growth rates in the study of growth analysis of individual plants and is effectively applied in the files of botany (Hunt, 1982) (Hoffman & Poorter, 2002; Ganjihah & Keshava, 2015). Doubling time (Dt.) is defined as the time to be taken to double in the size or value and exists a direct equivalence between the relative growth rate and the doubling time (Ganjihah & Keshava, 2015).

$$RGR = \frac{W2-W1}{T2-T1}$$

where W1=natural log of initial number of publications

W2= natural log of final number of publications after a specific period of interval

T2-T1= the unit difference between the initial and final time.

Doubling Time (Dt.) = $\frac{\log e^2}{R}$ = 0.693/R where, R is the Relative Growth Rate

It is observed that the value of Relative Growth Rate (RGR) (Keshava, Ganjihah, & Gowda, 2008) decreased from 0.70 in the year 1998 to 0.05 in the year 2022 with average Relative Growth Rate of 0.14. The values of doubling Time (Dt.) of publications increased over period from 0.98 in the year 1998 to 14.46 during 2022, with highest doubling time recorded in the year 2020 with 19.32.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics (comparative statistics for different block periods)

5 Years Block period	Publications	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Sample Variance	Kurtosis	Skewness (β2)
1998-2002	230	46	46	4.58	21	0.81	-0.83
2003-2007	233	46.6	46	5.81	33.8	-0.15	-0.69
2008-2012	260	52	58	10.30	106	-2.22	-0.77
2013-2017	315	63	62	14.97	224	2.22	0.66
2018-2022	287	57.4	61	11.15	124.3	-0.50	-0.38

Table 2, interpret the dispersion using statistical parameters. Standard deviation for is an important absolute measure of dispersion. The value of standard deviation clearly shows that the publications are dispersed largely for all the periods; the dispersion is very high for 2013-2017 from the starting year 1998-2002. The highest mean number of articles is observed 315 in the years block 2013-2017 and least mean is observed 46 for the years 1998-2002.

Skewness helps to study the shape of the distribution while kurtosis refers to the flatness or peakedness of the curve. The distribution for the literature is negatively skewed for all the block periods except 2013-2017 with max 0.66.

Application of Growth Models

Table 3 shows the application of growth models (Linear, Exponential and Power) on Research literature on Pollination for 25 years from 1998 to 2022.

Table 3 Application of Growth models (R² value)

Sl.	Growth Models	R value
1	Linear	0.2847
2	Exponential	0.2912
3	Power	0.2912

The R² value for the data is reflected in the table. It is clear from the table that, during the study period growth of Pollination literature does not fits for linear, exponential, or power trend lines.

Figure 1 Linear growth trend line for Pollination literature

Figure 2 Exponential growth trend line for Pollination literature

Figure 3 Power growth trend line for Pollination literature

Figure 1, 2 and 3 presents the graphs on data for the growth models Linear, Exponential and Power respectively. It reveals that the trend line does not fits for the study period.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study carried out to measure the trends in various aspects of published literature on Pollination research indexed in the CABI database for the period 1998 to 2022 (25 years). It is observed that, total 1,325 research publications with no consistent growth of publications for entire study period varies between 3.87% (38) to 4.68% (62) publications, except for the year 2021 with 5.36% (71) and for the year 2014 with 6.49% (86) highest publications. Relative Growth Rate (RGR) decreased from 0.70 in the year 1998 to 0.05 in the year 2022 with average Relative Growth Rate of 0.14. The Doubling Time (Dt.) of publications increased over period from 0.98 in the year 1998 to 14.46. The distribution for global literature is negatively skewed for all the block periods except 2013-202017. Growth of Pollination literature does not fit for Linear, Exponential and Power trend lines. Pollination is important in the yield of most crop species and contributes to one-third of global crop production, the study concludes that, even

though the pollination is very important for a strong, healthy ecosystem and crop production, there no consistent trend towards increased growth of literature in the field of Pollination for the study period.

References

1. Agrios, G. N. (2005). *Plant Pathology* (5th ed.). Burlington, MA: Elsevier Academic Press.
2. Arunachalam, S., & Umarani. (2021). Mapping agricultural research in India: a profile based on CAB Abstracts 1998. *Current Science*, 81(8), 896-906.
3. Ganjihal, G. A., & Keshava. (2008). Scientometric dimensions of Astronomy and Astrophysics research in India (2001-2010): A study based on SCI. *Indian Journal of Library and Information Technology*, 4(4), 14-18.
4. Ganjihal, G. A., & Keshava. (2015). Frontiers in Radio Astronomy Research in India (1999-2012): A scientometric study. *e-Library Science Research Journal*, 5(3), 1-10.
5. Ganjihal, G. A., & Keshava. (2015). Growth pattern of Indian Radio Astronomy literature (1999-2012): a scientometric study. *Indian Journal of Library and Information Technology*, 5, 13-15.
6. Ganjihal, G. A., Ganjihal, V. A., & Kwati, K. S. (2023). Bradford's law applicability to the Pollination research: A bibliometric study. *International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 10(2), 47-54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17148/IARJSET.2023.10207>
7. Hoffman, W. A., & Poorter, H. (2002). Avoiding bias in calculations of relative growth rate. *Annals of Botany*, 90(1), 37-42.
8. Keshava, AN, Chennakumaraswamy., Ganjihal, G. A., & H, Lokesh. (2010). A Scientometric Portrait of Prof. S.S. Kubakaddi. *Pearl: A Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(1), 21-27.
9. Liu, B., Zhang, L., & Wang, X. (2017). Scientometric profile of gobal rice research during 1985-2014. *Current Science*, 112(5), 1003-1011.
10. Sangam, S. L., Liming, L., & Ganjihal, G. A. (2010). Modeling the growth of Indian and Chinese liquid crystals literature as reflected in Science Citation Index (1997–2006). *Scientometrics*, 84(1), 49-52. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0079-x>
11. Hunt, R. (1982). Plant growth analysis: Second derivates and compounded second derivates of splined plant growth curves. *Annals of Botany*, 50, 317-328. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.aob.a086371>
12. Hoffmann, W.A., & Poorter, H. (2002). Avoiding bias in calculations of relative growth rate. *Annals of Botany*, 80, 37-42.
13. Gupta, B.M., Sharma, P., & Karisiddappa, C.R. (1997). Growth of research literature in scientific specialities: A modeling perspective. *Scientometrics*, 40(3), 507-528. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02459297>
14. Egghe, L., & Ravichandra Rao, I.K. (1992). Classification of growth models based on growth rate and its applications. *Scientometrics*, 25, 5-46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02016845>
15. Hadagali, G.S. & Anandhalli, G. (2015). Modeling the Growth of Neurology Literature. *J. of in fo sci. theory and practice* 3(3), 45-63.
16. Nayak, S. & Bankapur, V.M. (2018). Modeling the growth of Indian agricultural literature: a scientometric study based on WOS-SCIE. 7th National Conference of Institute of Scientometrics on Libraries in the Sharing Economy
17. Ganjihal, G. A., Ganjihal, V. A., & Kwati, K. S. (2023). Modeling the Growth of Bacterial Blight. *International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 10(2), 140-145. doi:<https://doi.org/10.17148/IARJSET.2023.10224>
18. CABI. (2023, March 03). About CAB Direct. Retrieved from <https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/about>
19. Inouye, D. W. (2013). Role of Pollination. *Encyclopaedia of Biodiversity*. 140-146.
20. Smithsonian Gardens (n.d). The Why, What, When, Where, Who, How of Pollination accessed on Feb 26, 2023 from <https://gardens.si.edu/gardens/pollinator-garden/why-what-when-where-who-how-pollination/>
21. Klatt, B. K. et.al. (2014). Bee pollination improves crop quality, shelf life and commercial value. *Proc. R. Soc. B* 281: 20132440. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.2440>.

22. TNAU. (n.d.). Apiculture: Bee Flora and pollination of crops. Retrieved February 20, 2023, from https://agritech.tnau.ac.in/farm_enterprises/fe_api_beefloraapollin.html